

The Temple Scroll

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Jewish Traditions, Late Second Temple Judaism, Text, Scripture, Ritual text, Early Jewish Literature, Dead Sea Scrolls, Temple Buildings and Temple Cult, Rewritten Scripture

The Temple Scroll is the longest of the Dead Sea Scrolls, with its prime exemplar, 11QTemplea (11Q19), extending to just over eight metres long. For eleven years after its discovery, the manuscript lay hidden beneath the floorboards of an antiquities dealer in Bethlehem, before being acquired by Israeli archaeologist Yigael Yadin in 1967 and eventually published in 1977. 11Q19 is dated paleographically to the end of the first century BCE or beginning of the first century CE. A further five manuscripts associated with the Temple Scroll have been subsequently identified and published. The oldest extant manuscript, 4QRouleau du Temple (4Q524) shows considerable overlap with 11Q19 and was dated by its editor, Émile Puech, to c. 150–125 BCE in the early Hasmonean period. Also found in Cave 4 was 4QTemple? (4Q365a), dated to 125–75 BCE. There are significant differences between the fragments which comprise 4Q365a and 11Q19, and it was therefore more likely a source for the Temple Scroll than a copy. Two further manuscripts from Cave 11 have been identified with the Temple Scroll, 11QTempleb (11Q20) and 11QTemplec (11Q21). They have been dated to the first half of the first century CE, and whilst it is clear that 11Q20 is a copy of the Temple Scroll, 11Q21 is too fragmentary to allow for certainty. In 2015, several small fragments from Cave 5 were identified as a further copy of the Temple Scroll and labelled 5QTemplea (5Q21). 5Q21 was dated paleographically to 75–50 BCE by its editor, Alexei Yuditsky. Various dates have been proposed for the Temple Scroll's composition, ranging from the fifth century BCE to the early first century BCE. The discovery and identification of 4Q524 gave a latest possible date of the end of the second century BCE. Though Yadin identified the composition with the community at Qumran, 4Q524 pre-dates the Qumran settlement. This, combined with the absence of key sectarian terminology, suggests that the Temple Scroll's origins should be located in a broader social milieu. The contents of the Temple Scroll indicate an interest in the Temple, cultic practices, and an elevated status for the High Priest. It may therefore have emerged from priestly circles. The author/redactor presents the composition as a new Torah, beginning with material from the covenant renewal ceremony in Exodus 34 and continuing through to laws from Deuteronomy. Biblical law is "rewritten" according to the interpretation of the author/redactor and their community, often as first-person speech direct from the mouth of God himself. At the heart of the composition is the description of a plan for a new Temple and its courts (cols. 3–13; 30–45). Alongside the Temple plan are prescriptions for religious festivals and Temple worship (cols. 13–29), purity laws (cols. 45–51), and the Deuteronomic Paraphrase (cols. 51–66), which is an elaboration on a series of Deuteronomic laws. The latter includes the Law of the King (cols. 56–59), which offers a distinctive treatment of kingship. The Scroll is likely composed of several sources, some of which may have circulated independently prior to their incorporation into the scroll by a redactor.

Date Range: 450 BCE - 125 BCE

Region: Jerusalem and the Judean Desert

Region tags: Middle East, Israel, Palestine, Judah, Qumran, Israel in the Second Temple period

Jerusalem and the Judean Desert, including the Qumran site

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Yadin, Yigael. *The Temple Scroll*. 3 Vols. Jerusalem: Israel Exploration Society, 1983.
- Source 2: Schiffman, Lawrence H., and Andrew Gross. *The Temple Scroll: 11Q19, 11Q20, 11Q21, 4Q524, 5Q21 with 4Q365a*. Leiden, The Netherlands: Brill, 2021.
- Source 3: White Crawford, Sidnie. *The Temple Scroll and Related Texts*. Sheffield, Sheffield Academic Press, 2000.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <http://dss.collections.imj.org.il/temple>
- Source 1 Description: High resolution images of 11Q19
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive>
- Source 2 Description: A searchable archive of high definition spectral images including photographs of 4Q365a, 4Q524, 11Q20, 11Q21, and 5Q21

General Variables

Materiality

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

- Other textile: Parchment

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

- Physical preparation

Notes: Roman Schuetz's 2017 study found evidence of an unusual parchment manufacturing technique behind the parchment of 11Q19. The extremely thin skin was coated with an inorganic layer, which was applied to the flesh side of the skin to form a smooth writing surface.

Reference: Schuetz, Roman, Janille Maragh, James Weaver, Ira Rabin, and Admir Masic. "The Temple Scroll: Reconstructing an Ancient Manufacturing Practice". *Science Advances* 5, no. 9 (September 6, 2019).

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

- Yes

- ↳ Tomb
 - No
- ↳ Cemetery
 - No
- ↳ Temple
 - No
- ↳ Shrine
 - No
- ↳ Altar
 - No
- ↳ Devotional marker
 - No
- ↳ Cenotaph
 - No
- ↳ Church
 - No
- ↳ Mosque
 - No
- ↳ Synagogue
 - No
- ↳ Triumphal Arch
 - No
- ↳ Monument
 - No

↳ Mass Gathering Point

– No

↳ Cave(s)

– Yes

↳ Hilltops

– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– No

↳ Library/archive

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There are various hypotheses about the function and purpose of the site at Qumran and the caves where the scrolls were found. It is possible that the collection of scrolls could have formed some kind of library.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The text was composed in a pre-canonical era but it was likely considered authoritative in some sense. The composition presents itself as the words of God, thereby making a significant claim to authority. We cannot be sure how it was received by the communities that read and preserved it.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– Yes

↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?

– No

↳ Possess its own distinct written language?

– No

Notes: The Temple Scroll is "rewritten Scripture" and draws heavily on Pentateuchal texts, using the words and language of these texts but imbuing them with new meaning.

↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?

– I don't know

Notes: To distinguish between a "religious" and "non-religious" institution in Hasmonean Judea would be anachronistic. The Temple, for instance, fulfilled both cultic and economic functions, and the High Priest often operated in the political sphere.

↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support religious study of text?

– I don't know

↳ Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?

– I don't know

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We cannot be sure which group or community produced the Temple Scroll, but several laws in the Scroll suggest some level of hostility towards Gentiles.

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Field doesn't know

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Field doesn't know

Is there material significance to the text?

– Yes

↳ Is it visible?

– Yes

↳ Is it hidden?

– No

↳ Can it be touched?

– Yes

↳ Does touching the text during ritual have a specific function?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does the material significance have an esoteric function?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does the text serve a protective function?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does the text serve a healing function?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does the text serve a cleansing function?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does the text serve as a form of expiation?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Has the materiality of the text been altered?

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Specify: The first five columns of 11Q19 are written in a different hand to the rest of the scroll. It is likely the beginning of the scroll was damaged and the pages containing the first five columns were then replaced.

↳ Are there debates about whether or not altering the materiality of the text is acceptable?

– No

↳ Are there material substance that commonly accompany the text?

Please specify the substances in the sub-questions

– Field doesn't know

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: One of the manuscripts, 4Q365a, consists of five fragments. Yigael Yadin considered two of the

fragments, along with frg. 23 of 4Q365, to belong to a copy of the Temple Scroll. The DJD editors of these fragments, Sidnie White Crawford and Emanuel Tov, published them as 4QTemple?, arguing that they were more likely source material for the Temple Scroll. The fragments contain similar themes to those found in the Temple Scroll and one of the fragments parallels some text from 11Q19, though the 4Q365a text is shorter.

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?
– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: By virtue of where the Temple Scroll manuscripts were found, they are part of the group of texts known as the Dead Sea Scrolls.

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?
– No

Notes: The Temple Scroll was composed prior to the formation of the canon, though most likely certain compositions were considered to be authoritative. The Temple Scroll's use of wording from the Pentateuch to lend an aura of authority is indicative of the importance of the Pentateuchal texts to the community. However, the freedom with which the author/redactor "re-wrote" those Pentateuchal texts as new, divine law is evidence of the fluidity of what comprised "Scripture" at the time.

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?
– Field doesn't know

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Behavioral literature?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Other
–Other [specify]: Rewritten Scripture

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual manual

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The High Priest is to be replaced by his son (11Q19 15:15-16). The king is to marry a woman from the house of his father (11Q19 57:17) and should he follow the law, his descendants will sit on the throne of Israel forever (11Q19 col.59).

↳ Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– Yes

↳ Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– Field doesn't know

↳ How is the lineage established?

– Blood or Marriage relations

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– Yes

↳ Are there formal institutions merged with the state or polity of the religious group?

– Yes

Notes: Laws are given for the king as cols. 57-59. His authority appears to be subordinated to that of the High Priest, whose permission must be sought before war is entered into. In addition, the king is not given any kind of cultic role.

↳ Is there an institutionalized police force whose behavior is dictated by the legal code?

– No

↳ Is there an institutionalized judicial system whose behavior is dictate by the legal code?

– Yes

↳ Does the text in question specify institutionalized punishment?

– Yes

↳ Execution?

– Yes

↳ Exile?

– No

Notes: Exile will be a punishment for Israel should they not follow God's laws (11Q19 col. 59), but it is a punishment meted out by God, rather than an institutionalized punishment.

↳ Corporal punishments?

– Yes

↳ Ostracism?

– No

↳ Seizure of property?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there any established institutionalized rewards specified in the text?

– No

– Yes

↳ Are there formal institutions merged with the state or polity of the religious group?

– I don't know

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– Yes

↳ What is the arrangement of the calendar? [Select all that apply]

– Solar?

↳ Does the calendar specifically dictate acceptable times for certain activities?

– Yes

↳ Planting?

– No

↳ Water management? (such as opening or closing dams/dykes)

– No

↳ Harvest?

– Yes

↳ Naming ceremonies (for toddlers)?

– No

↳ "First haircuts" (pre-teen)

– No

↳ Ceremonies marking puberty/entry into adulthood?

– Yes

Notes: Details of a ceremony are not given, but when a boy reaches 20 years he must give half a shekel as his redemption to the Lord. Only then can he enter the Temple's Middle Court (11Q19:7-11).

↳ Marriage?

– No

↳ House construction (often a metaphor for marriage)?

– No

↳ Divorce?

– No

↳ Warfare?

– No

↳ Funerary services?

– No

↳ Trade/commerce?

– No

↳ Festivals?

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals?

–Specify: Various festivals are held throughout the year.

↳ Pilgramages?

– Yes

↳ How strict are the stipulations regarding pilgrimage?

–obligatory for some

↳ Is encouraging pilgrimages a primary reason for the existence of the text?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are pilgrimages guided by the text associated with particular life events?

– No

↳ Does pilgrimage guided by this text involve/follow major routes/roads?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the pilgrimage conducted by walking or by other means?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Feasting?

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed in accordance with the guidelines of the text?

– Yes

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that produced the text/copies of the text?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific locations in accordance with guidelines from the text?

– Yes

↳ Specify

–Specify: Festival offerings are eaten in the courtyards of the Temple.

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Notes: There is no concept of an afterlife as such, but 11Q19 29:9-10 speaks of a Temple established by God himself which will last for all time. This is not an other-worldly hope, but it looks forward to an eschatological Temple when Israel is fully restored.

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Cremation?

– No

↳ Mummification?

– No

↳ Interment?

– No

↳ Cannibalism?

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying)?

– No

↳ Feeding to animals?

– No

↳ Secondary burial?

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse?

– No

↳ Are there specific designations for parts of corpses?

– No

↳ Could parts of corpses become transformed into partial bodily relics?

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse?

– Yes

Notes: 11Q19 col. 48 specifies that special areas must be set aside outside the cities for the burial of corpses. Particular rituals must also be followed after contact with a corpse.

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: 11Q19 col.26 refers to Azazel in the context of the Day of Atonement. In other Second Temple texts, Azazel is described as a demon figure, but we cannot be certain of the meaning of Azazel in the Temple Scroll.

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Field doesn't know

Notes: See above re Azazel.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Notes: The Scroll speaks of God dwelling with his people forever when they fulfil all the sacrificial and cultic requirements given in the Festival Calendar (11Q19 col.29). This is not a physical presence however, but it is God's "glory" that will settle on the Temple.

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: Azazel - see note above.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– I don't know

Notes: 11Q19 col.59 speaks of the king who does not follow God's commands being "cut off". The act of punishing, however, is not attributed to any particular being.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Notes: There is no specific reference to a Messiah, however the language used of the king who will follow God's statutes in 11Q19 col. 59 echoes that of 1 Kgs 6 regarding Solomon. The king's descendants shall sit on the throne of Israel forever.

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– Yes

↳ At specified time in future

– No

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– Field doesn't know

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– Field doesn't know

↳ At some other time [specify]

– Yes

Notes: According to 11Q19 col.29, God will establish his eschatological Temple for all times "on the day of blessing".

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end

– No

↳ Divine judgment event

– No

↳ Restoration of the world

– No

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle

– I don't know

↳ Establishment of new political system

– Yes

↳ Establishment of new religious system

– Yes

Notes: Not precisely a new religious system, but a new Temple built and administered as God intends.

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?

– Yes

↳ All religious in-group members will survive

– I don't know

↳ A subset of the religion in-group members will survive

– I don't know

↳ All members of the sample region will survive

– No

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton

– I don't know

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– No

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

↳ Generosity/charity

– I don't know

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– No

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– I don't know

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

↳ Cooperation

– I don't know

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– No

↳ Moderation/frugality

– No

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– No

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– I don't know

↳ Strength (physical)

– Yes

↳ Power/status/nobility

– Yes

↳ Humility/modesty

– Yes

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– I don't know

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– Yes

↳ Optimism/hope

– Yes

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– I don't know

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– Yes

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males)

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (females)

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males)

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (females)

– Yes

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– Yes

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– Yes

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– Yes

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– Yes

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Cleaning rituals must take place whenever someone has died in the house (11Q19 col. 49).

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– I don't know

Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– Field doesn't know

Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Yes

Are there orthopraxy checks?

– Yes

Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– Field doesn't know

Is there use of intoxicants?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification?

– No

↳ Circumcision?

– No

↳ Food taboos?

– Yes

↳ Hair?

– No

↳ Dress?

– Yes

↳ Ornaments?

– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?
 - No
- ↳ Are there material offerings present?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are they mandatory?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings? (I.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')
 - No
- ↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?
 - Yes
 - ↳ By the community?
 - Yes
 - ↳ By specific individuals?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is it required?
 - Yes

- ↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance)?
 - Yes
- ↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff?
 - Field doesn't know

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

- Other

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

- A Spiritual Elect

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

- No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

- No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

- No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

- Field doesn't know

Notes: We do not know exactly where and when the Temple Scroll was read and taught.

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– Yes

Notes: A council of 12 is to be appointed by the king according to 11Q19 col. 57. Their role is to judge and make decisions relating to the law.

Does the text regulate bureaucracy permanently?

– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy temporarily/seasonally?

– No

↳ Does the text dictate how the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group?

– Yes

↳ Does the text dictate how individuals interact with other institutional bureaucracies?

– No

↳ Does the text regulate the primary supporting income of the place?

– I don't know

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out land?

– No

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out tools?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– Yes

↳ Does the text require the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes?

– Yes

↳ Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– I don't know

↳ Is taxation linked to an understanding of charitable giving?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– Yes

↳ Power to conscript?

– Yes

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

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